

INTERNACIONAL CONFERENCE
ON TECHNOLOGICAL INNOVATION
IN BUILDING

8^o CONGRESO INTERNACIONAL

INNOVACION TECNOLOGICA EDIFICACION

DEPARTAMENTO DE TECNOLOGÍA DE LA EDIFICACIÓN

Escuela Técnica Superior de Edificación de Madrid

Avda. Juan de Herrera Nº 6 28040 Madrid

CITE 2023

22, 23 & 24 MARZO

Patrocinan:

Libro de abstracts
Abstract book

POLITÉCNICA

CITE

VIII Congreso Internacional de Innovación
Tecnológica en Edificación.

VIII International conference on Technological
Innovation in Building

UNIVERSIDAD
POLITÉCNICA
DE MADRID

Escuela Técnica
Superior de
Edificación

CONSEJO GENERAL
DE LA ARQUITECTURA TÉCNICA
DE ESPAÑA

ESCUELA TÉCNICA SUPERIOR DE EDIFICACIÓN

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Universidad Politécnica de Madrid

Patrocinador:

URSA Ibérica Aislantes

Depósito Legal: M-6332-2023

CITE 2023 ABSTRACTS INDEX**Achievements**

- THERMAL CONDUCTIVE BEHAVIORS ANALYSIS D PRINTED HOLLOW BRICK** 14
Hamidreza Babaeyan Ahmadi; Jorge Gallego Sánchez-Torija

Building Environment

- EVOLUTION OF THE HEAT STRESS INDEX OF THE CITY OF MADRID USING THE URBCLIM CLIMATE MODEL OF THE EUROPEAN SPACE AGENCY** 19

David Hidalgo García;

- CEMENT COBBLESTONES LIGHTENED WITH INDUSTRIAL POLYMERIC WASTE** 21
Raquel Arroyo; Sara Gutiérrez-González; Sara González Moreno; Lourdes Alameda Cuenca-Romero; Álvaro Alonso; Verónica Calderón.

- MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF MORTAR CONTAINING WASTE FOUNDRY SAND** 22
Ahlem Akeb; Souad Kherbache; Abdelkader Tahakourt,

- REHABILITATION IN THE ENERGY FIELD IN SPAIN AND ITALY: THE COMPARISON** 24
Alessio, Maria Rosaria; Citroz, Annalaura; Palocci, Elisa; Scafuri, Alice; Aguilera Benito, Patricia; Bach Buendía, Isabel; Lopez-Asiain Martínez, Juan; Viccione Giacomo.

- MONITORING OF PM. IN RESIDENTIAL BUILDINGS IN NORTHERN SPAIN** 26
Alejandro Payán de Tejada Alonso; José Fernández Castillo; Juan López-Asiain Martínez; Sara Aragón Chicharro

- THE INFLUENCE OF DIRECT/INDIRECT LIGHTING SYSTEMS ON COGNITIVE RESPONSE IN VIRTUAL REALITY** 28
Nuria Castilla; Juan Luis Higuera-Trujillo; Carmen Llinares

- STUDY OF THE MECHANICAL BEHAVIOR OF PLASTER WITH POLYAMIDES.** 30
Marta Rodríguez-Aybar; Manuel Alejandro Pedreño-Rojas; César Porrás-Amores; M^a Esther Moreno Fernández.

- PAST, PRESENT AND FUTURE OF THE MECHANISMS OF THE CANAL DE CASTILLA** 31
Ángel Mariano Rodríguez Pérez; Lucía Olmo Rodríguez; Cesar Antonio Rodríguez; Julio José Caparros Mancera; Jose Antonio Hernández Torres

- MULTIFUNCTIONAL PARK TO CONTRIBUTE TO SOCIAL INTEGRATION** 33
Wendy Alexandra Estrada Maximiliano

- THE BENEFITS OF THE REPRODUCTION AND EXPLOITATION OF THE NATURAL PROCESS OF INFILTRATION OF RUNOFF.** 38
Evelio Teijón López-Zuazo; Álvaro González Payo

- THE ROLE OF BUILDING-INTEGRATED GREENERY SYSTEMS ON BUILDING'S SUSTAINABILITY CERTIFICATIONS** 41
Marcelo Reyes; Gabriel Perez; Julia Coma

- CONFLICT MANAGEMENT PROCEDURE IN CONSTRUCTION COMPANIES.** 43
Nazaret Morera de la Torre; Miriam Zamora Calleja; Cristina Calderón Gallo; Mercedes del Río Merino.

- EFFECTS OF THE GROUND TEMPERATURE HYPOTHESES ON THE ENERGY PERFORMANCE GAP OF IN-USE BUILDINGS. A CASE STUDY IN ALMERIA** 45
*,Lapuenta C.S.; *Soutullo S.; Sánchez M.N.; Giancola E.; ,Jiménez M.J.*

- SUSTAINABILITY DIAGNOSIS OF EDUCATIONAL CENTERS' PERFORMANCE AND TOOL DEVELOPMENT TO INCREASE THE COMPETENCIES OF THE EDUCATIONAL COMMUNITY** 47
José Alberto Díaz; Silvia Soutullo; Emanuela Giancola; María Nuria Sanchez; Ana Rosa Gamarra; Carmen Lago; Yolanda Lechón; Israel Marqués Valderrama; Ricardo Chacartegui; Jose Antonio Becerra

- VOLUMETRIC DISTRIBUTION FOR THE USE OF SOLAR ENERGY. A CASE STUDY IN SORIA, SPAIN** 49
Santiago Tomás Fondoso Ossola; Irene Martini; Emanuela Giancola; Silvia Soutullo

- INVARIANTS OF POPULAR CONSTRUCTION IN SUSTAINABILITY** 51

<i>Gregorio García López de la Osa; Ricardo Tendero Caballero; Inmaculada Martínez Pérez</i>	
THE IMPORTANCE OF A CORRECT MANAGEMENT OF CONSTRUCTION AND DEMOLITION WASTE FOR THE CIRCULAR ECONOMY	53
<i>Alejandra Vidales Barriguete; Carolina Piña Ramírez; Katarzyna Kalinowska-Wichrowska</i>	
ENHANCING HYDROPHILICITY AND SELF-CLEANING PROPERTIES OF BUILDING GLASSES USING FE DOPED TiO₂ PREPARED BY SOL-GEL METHOD	55
<i>Ehsan MehmandoustEsfahani, Antonio Nieto-Márquez, José Antonio Díaz López</i>	
ANALYSIS OF A LIVING UNIT'S BEHAVIOR WITH PASSIVE AIR CONDITIONING SYSTEMS LOCATED IN THE CITY OF GRANADA	57
<i>Nelson Galvis; Denisse González; María Fernanda Rodríguez</i>	
WALNUT AND HAZELNUT SHELLS FOR INSULATING PANELS FABRICATION	60
<i>Luisa Errico; Arisbel Cerpa-Naranjo; Javier Pérez-Piñero</i>	
STRATEGIES FOR THE ENERGY TRANSITION OF THE CONSTRUCTION SECTOR IN THE PROVINCE OF LLEIDA (CATALUÑA, SPAIN)	62
<i>Claudia Marín; Gabriel Pérez; Alvaro de Gracia; Juliá Coma</i>	
	Building Technology
DRONES AS A TOOL FOR TAKING DATA ON FACADES	64
<i>Enrique Parra-Albarracín; Irene Ros-Martín</i>	
VIRTUAL REALITY IN BUILDING, A NEW WAY TO GET IN BUILDING PROCESSES.	67
<i>Manuel Álvarez Dorado, Mercedes Valiente Lopez, Alejandra Vidales Barriguete, Patricia Aguilera Benito, Carolina Piña Ramírez, Alicia Zargoza Benzal, Tomás Gil López, Pedro Palmero Cabezas, Isabel Bach Buendía</i>	
A REVIEW OF THE APPLICATION OF PREFABRICATED STRUCTURES USING BUILDING INFORMATION MODELING	69
<i>Amirhossein Javaherikhah, Samane Khezli, Mercedes Valiente Lopez</i>	
AN OVERVIEW OF THE IMPACT OF RENEWABLE ENERGIES IN THE ARCHITECTURE OF ZERO ENERGY BUILDINGS	71
<i>Amirhossein Javaherikhah, Samane Khezli, Mercedes Valiente Lopez</i>	
YIELD LINES METHOD THROUGHOUT FINITE ELEMENT METHOD. APPLICATIONS WITH SAP000	73
<i>José Javier Ferrán Gozávez; Carlos Manuel Ferrer Gisbert ; Miguel Redón Santafé; Esteban Gargallo Tatay; Juan Bautista Torregrosa Soler; Francisco Javier Sánchez Romero</i>	
DSF-PCM BUILDING ENERGY PERFORMANCE ASSESSMENT: A CASE STUDY IN VALENCIA, SPAIN	75
<i>Niloufar Ziasistani; Andrés Meana-Fernández; Juan Manuel González-Caballín Sánchez; Antonio José Gutiérrez-Trashorras</i>	
PROPOSAL OF A PILOT FORMATIVE EXPERIENCE FOR THE SUBJECT TECHNICAL SYSTEMS APPLIED IN THE DESIGN OF A RIGID ORIGAMI KINETIC PAVILION.	77
<i>Pablo Miguel De Souza Sánchez, Fernando Martínez Soto</i>	
EFFECTIVENESS OF PLANT EXTRACTS TO PREVENT CHLORIDE-INDUCED CORROSION IN REINFORCED CONCRETE.	81
<i>Jennifer Pérez; María Fernanda Rodríguez; Kevin Rene Chillan Simbaña</i>	
METHODOLOGY FOR THE CHARACTERISATION OF ENERGY PERFORMANCE AND COMFORT ACCORDING TO DWELLING TYPOLOGY AND USAGE	83
<i>Jose Manuel Lorenzo Gallardo; Beatriz Montalbán Pozas; Marta Lucas Bonilla; Silvia Sierra Álvarez; Francisco Serrano Candela, Lucas Bonilla Rodríguez, Pablo Bustos García de Castro</i>	
EVALUATION OF THE MECHANICAL BEHAVIOR OF HYDRAULIC LIME MORTARS WITH POLYPROPYLENE FIBER ADDITION	85
<i>Belén Cabrera; María Isabel Prieto; Alfonso Cobo</i>	

PROPOSAL OF A PILOT FORMATIVE EXPERIENCE FOR THE SUBJECT TECHNICAL SYSTEMS APPLIED IN THE DESIGN OF A RIGID ORIGAMI KINETIC PAVILION.

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Keywords: educational innovation, kinetic building, innovation in building, construction facilities, materials and construction systems.

Abstract

The Technical Systems subject, with six ECTS, is part of the Scientific-Technical training area of the Degree in Architecture, the second most extended module of contents of the degree (Chart 1), and a necessary step to take the Master's in Architecture offered at the *Universidad Europea de Canarias* [1], the first Master title offered in the region of Canary Islands that enables to practice the profession in Spain [2].

Table 1: Degree planning in Modules and ECTS of each (Own elaboration)

Module	ECTS
INTRODUCTORY MODULE: BASIC SCIENCES AND DRAWING	60
TECHNICAL MODULE: CONSTRUCTION, STRUCTURES AND FACILITIES	72
PROJECT MODULE: COMPOSITION, PROJECTS, AND URBAN PLANNING	108
MODULE OF TRANSVERSAL SUBJECTS OF THE UEC	24
PROFESSIONAL PRACTICES	12
FINAL DEGREE WORK	12

The course provides the student with an integrating, global and transversal vision of the facilities, construction, and structure in architecture, for the search for rational solutions and committed to functionality, economy, harmony, and environmental balance, which will affect the improvement of the architectural design.

The student develops the aptitude to identify the construction elements and systems of the projects, analyze them defining their function and compatibility, propose and solve the construction details and transfer them to their commissioning. Likewise, in this subject, the student develops the capacities to apply and adopt non-conventional

technologies in the processes of design and execution of structures, envelopes, and installations.

Figure 1: Examples of abstract origami. [3]

The proposed training experience is an introduction to the possibilities of abstract origami [4] applied into architecture (Figure 1), from the conforming and structural fold to the oblique space [5]. And mainly addresses the constructive design of a folded and kinetic laminar structure, which forms a continuous roof and wall (Figure 2), made with Origami folding patterns [6] and/or Origami tessellations [7].

Figure 2: Kinetic Pavilion made by the students Fabián Quintero, Juan Alberto Luis, Nicolás González and Carlota García Silván. [5]

Starting from the base of the experiences of previous subjects and courses of the teachers [8] and of the formative learning experiences of the students, both in the technical and project modules -Construction, Structures, and Installations as well as Composition, Projects, Urbanism (Figure 3) and the preparatory module of Basic Sciences and Drawing [9] -, in relation to terminology, concepts, functional, structural and constructive organization.

Figure 3: Kinetic origami pavilions design by the students Cristina Díaz and Raquel Martins. [3]

The objective of the practical exercises of the matter is to reflect on what has been learned and take initiatives, arriving at specific solutions with optimal results through iterations. The purpose is justified by presenting professional documentation applying the current technical building regulations with a critical vision of the technical specifications and innovative construction methods [10].

This subject directly relates the training activities with the contents, such as the study of industrialized systems in structure, infrastructure, exterior-interior envelope, advanced light facades, textile membranes and laminar surfaces. Finally, they are integrated into a "Technical System" known as "Integrated Design of the facilities in Architecture, Construction and Structures".

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